

How to diversify your department's seminar series

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Abstract

In the wake of the murder of George Floyd and the COVID-19 pandemic, there is renewed energy and commitment from institutions to create more inclusive, diverse and equitable spaces. One area where such efforts can have a significant impact is department seminar series. Seminar series are a key part of the academic model in the field of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology (EEB). They provide opportunities to both speakers and host departments through disseminating new research, networking, and forming new collaborations. By increasing the diversity of seminar speakers, we can aim to provide these critical opportunities to all members of the EEB community. Here we outline practices that have improved these efforts in our US-based department and additional ideas that can be adapted by other departments and disciplines. 1) Craft a mission statement for your seminar series that includes improving equity, diversity, and inclusion. 2) Evaluate if you are progressing towards that mission. 3) Give students some ownership over inviting seminar speakers. 4) Invite speakers from careers/positions other than senior faculty. 5) Allow speakers from marginalized backgrounds to talk about their research. 6) Offer remote and hybrid formats to speakers. 7) Pay speakers an honorarium. 8) Continue and expand your efforts over time. Incorporating seminar series in our efforts to increase the diversity, equity, and inclusion in the field has the potential for significant impact.

Introduction

The systematic exclusion of minoritized and historically marginalized communities throughout all of academia is a continued problem (Young, 2005; Clotfelter, 2005; Clauset, 2015). Social media campaigns such as #BlackinSTEM, #BlackoutSTEM and #BlackinNature helped bring awareness and uplift Black scientists last year (Norton, 2020), but academia as a whole needs to continue actively supporting these efforts. The discipline of EEB is in a unique position to directly contend with its long history of white supremacy, eugenics and white settler colonialism that is blatantly embedded in the field (Bacon, 2019; Trisos, 2021). We have a responsibility to acknowledge and address the anti-Blackness, Native invisibility and white supremacy that permeates all aspects of our discipline in order to make lasting change (Schell, 2020; Trisos, 2021). While there is a current wave of dedication to improving equity,

diversity, and inclusion (EDI, Box 1) in academia, in our experience the efforts of the broader community generally neglect seminar series. Diversifying your seminar series is an opportunity to benefit a broader array of speakers as well as the members of your own department (Table 1). Below we have highlighted some tactics that we have currently employed or plan to incorporate within our department (in a US institution) and some lessons we learned for continued improvement (Box 2).

Have A Mission Statement Including Increasing EDI

We found that our seminar series lacked a clear mission statement which hindered our efforts to create an effective seminar series. Because student and faculty departmental officials tend to operate on an *ad hoc* and individual basis, much institutional knowledge is lost when individuals cycle in and out of positions. This often requires new committee chairs to reinvent the wheel. A public document that explicitly lists goals and methods for the seminar committee is an essential tool to affect lasting change. These goals should incorporate the inclusion of a diverse group of invited speakers and equitable practices.

Evaluate Your Progress

Just as it is important to define goals, it is essential to define how to evaluate if those goals are being met. This requires documenting the invitation process and the experiences of speakers. This recordkeeping should not be exhaustive or intrusive for the invitee, and should record the changes made to the process year to year. Without a record, we have no frame of reference for how well we are succeeding or failing at our goals, or a means to identify needed improvements. A short anonymous survey of invitees on why they did or did not accept an invitation could expose previously overlooked issues impacting speakers from historically excluded and marginalized groups in STEM. This will allow the selection body to revise their methods to better meet the goal of a diverse speaker body. Scientists are used to this iterative process of setting goals, defining protocols, and evaluating outcomes; and the need to diversify seminar's speakers requires the same sort of systematic and mindful attitude. Without evaluating our progress toward our goal, we are likely guided by the many unconscious biases we all exhibit as individuals.

Engage Students In The Process

Based on our experience, directly involving students in the selection and invitation process contributed to diversifying the list of invited seminar speakers. We

have engaged students by having a seminar committee that includes several students and guarantees a minimum number of speakers that are nominated and voted on by the entire student body. Giving students such ownership has contributed to increasing speaker diversity for a few potential reasons. Nationally, there are discrepancies between student diversity and faculty diversity in STEM (National Science Foundation, 2019). When graduate students provide an opinion in this selection process, the speakers they invite may also reflect their diverse perspectives, thereby diversifying the seminar series. Graduate students by their nature will have fewer professional contacts than faculty members, making them less able to stay within their own circle for nominations. Further, as graduate students are starting their careers, they are incentivized to network outside their own circle to develop new professional relationships.

While incorporating students is important, we also caution others to consider the additional burden that may be imposed by asking specific graduate students of color to do this service work. This extra workload can contribute to their burden of the “minority tax” (Akin, 2020, Trejo, 2020, Jimenez et al. 2019) of being asked to do more EDI and general service work than their well-represented peers. For the 2020-2021 academic year, we solicited nominations from our Black graduate students and guaranteed a minimum number of speakers from their nominations. While this significantly increased the number of Black speakers for our seminars, we note that this added a significant burden to only the Black graduate students in addressing this needed change. Thus we recommend soliciting student involvement, but not specifically adding to the burdens of marginalized populations to address the need to improve seminar series diversity.

As enthusiastic as graduate students may be in participating in the selection of seminar speakers, effective change cannot be made without the help and support of faculty. One way faculty can show their commitment is to set a minimum number of spots per year for student-selected seminar speakers (ideally scaling with student body size). Such an action can show that faculty value graduate student input in shaping a department’s seminar series, as well as provide students ownership in the process. Creating a system of shared governance with graduate students is a key step in meeting equity, diversity, and inclusion goals.

Invite People From Various Careers, Stages And Systems

Historically, EEB in America has been dominated by white male researchers with recent surveys of faculty showing respondents to be ~85% white and over half male (Aubrey et al. 2020). Furthermore, EEB societies of English speakers show a distinct dropoff of gender and sexual identity diversity amongst tenured faculty (Rushworth et al. 2021). We look to diversify scientific perspectives by incorporating speakers who are not only tenured faculty from academic research institutions but also early-career

researchers, researchers outside of academia, and Indigenous leaders in the topic of Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK).

As previously noted, US tenured faculty are much more homogeneous in their identities than early career researchers. Thus incorporating early career scientists such as post-doctoral researchers and junior faculty can diversify your pool of seminar speakers. We recommend incorporating speakers outside major research universities such as the public sector, nonprofit or advocacy groups, and smaller academic institutions. This also benefits the host department by broadening scientific perspectives and expanding professional networks. Additionally, inviting Indigenous researchers and/or leaders in TEK will bring in a much-needed broader perspective (Gewin, 2021, Wheeler and Root-Bernstein 2020). We should look to form relationships with the communities whose land we are using for our research. We should strive to do this both out of respect for their agency and stewardship of the land, and because they may have expert knowledge we do not.

Inviting scientists and speakers from beyond the most recognized research universities not only exposes students and postdocs to alternative career paths, but also benefits minoritized groups by making more role models visible. Increasing visibility of diverse speakers in these seminars can empower and improve the inclusion and retention of underrepresented students (Drury, 2011). Furthermore, by diversifying the perspectives and experiences we incorporate in our field, our science will be better (Duffy *et. al* 2021).

Invite Marginalized Speakers To Talk About Their Research

When inviting diverse speakers to your institution, make sure you are inviting them to talk about their research and not just their experiences as a marginalized person in the field. Seminar series should provide all speakers with the same opportunities as outlined in Table 1. That said, there can be value for people to hear personal stories of what it is like to be a marginalized person in science. It can provide insights and understanding for non-marginalized people and/or people with different marginalized identities. It can also inspire and support students and early-career researchers from marginalized backgrounds. The best way to address the value of these conversations while giving all your speakers the same professional benefits is to allow them to discuss both topics if they choose to. If they want to take a deep dive into these important conversations you can provide them with an extended time slot or even a separate time slot to do so. You can provide space for talking about personal experiences as a marginalized person in science while still being sure to showcase their research the way you would for any other speaker.

Use Remote/Hybrid Model as an Advantage

Remote and hybrid seminars provide advantages that can contribute to devisifying seminar series. Advantages for remote seminars include opportunities for distantly located speakers (including international speakers) to participate in seminar series thus creating a wider pool of researchers. For instance, we had speakers from Qatar, Panama, and Portugal recently give online seminars in our department. Remote and hybrid seminars can also increase availability of seminars to the public through recording, potentially increasing the reach and impact of a given seminar. Remote options also allow speakers to participate with fewer barriers such as the time/energy needed to travel, indirect financial expenses, etc (Table 2). Despite these advantages, departments should not relegate all speakers from marginalized backgrounds to remote participation only. One reason is because online seminars provide different networking value to the invited speaker and attendees. When inviting a speaker, the best option for determining if it should be fully remote is simply to let the speaker choose. When constructing the hybrid model, it is critical to have similarly diverse representation from online speakers and on-campus speakers.

Compensate Speakers

The importance of compensation for the cost and work of giving an invited seminar has only increased in recent years, especially during COVID-19 and expanding racial inequities. In 2021, our department reinstated a \$500 seminar speaker honorarium after students and potential speakers spoke out about the importance of honoraria in increasing equity and inclusion for speakers. Some argue the cost of visiting an institution and the exposure of the talk is sufficient compensation since giving seminar talks is required to advance in academia. However, we note that this perspective caters to those with resources to easily offset the financial and personal costs of giving a seminar talk (Table 2). This creates a barrier for researchers with more limited resources. To combat this barrier, we recommend offering an honorarium. For speakers who express that they do not require such compensation, we recommend donating the earmarked funds to support other departmental EDI efforts. Financially compensating speakers can help offset the disproportionately limited resources that marginalized speakers typically have access to.

Sustain Your Efforts

There is a useful idea that you will never “arrive” as an ally but rather must always continue to practice allyship. That is to say, efforts to support marginalized people must be an ongoing and continually evolving process. Reading this and other opinion pieces on how to improve your equity, diversity, and inclusion efforts is only a

step in this process. Next steps include implementing these recommendations and measuring the impact of these efforts. As we improve on the current state of academia, other issues facing marginalized groups will surface to the forefront of our collective consciousnesses. We must continue to pay attention to the climate around us to identify what allyship practices need to be retooled or added to our efforts.

Conclusion

In this comment piece we have outlined both implemented and planned practices in our Ecology and Evolutionary Biology department seminar series at the University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA) to improve the overall diversity of our seminar speakers. Our recommendations come from our specific experiences within an US institution so we are speaking primarily to the culture of English speaking and primarily white institutions. While each department has individual goals and culture around their seminar series, we believe these guidelines can be applied and adapted for any department. Seminar series chairs and committees across departments and even fields can improve the diversity of their speakers using these approaches.

Identify and state your specific objectives for the seminar series as well as diversifying the speakers. Measure your success and areas of growth in meeting those objectives. Include students directly in the process of nominating and selecting speakers. Invite speakers from a variety of career stages and even non-university research institutions such as local conservation agencies and community science projects. Give your speakers and audience the opportunity to engage not only with the personal background of the speaker but also their science. Be equitable in supporting your invited speakers by offering remote options and providing honoraria. Sustain these efforts and be prepared to grow and adapt your efforts as the climate in academia changes. Implementing these guidelines has been successful in improving the diversity, equity, and inclusion of our seminar series and we hope this comment piece will provide a road map for other institutions to do so as well.

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Definitions

Equity: providing appropriate resources to people based on their needs to promote equal outcomes.

Diversity: variation in race, ethnicity, gender identity, sexual orientation, nationality, religion, and disability.

Inclusion: actively seeking out and creating a sense of belonging for diverse people.

Box 1. Definitions of relevant vocabulary.

Strategies to Improve Diversity of Your Department's Seminar Series

Have A Mission Statement Including Increasing EDI

Evaluate Your Progress

Involve Students in the Process

Invite People From Various Careers, Stages And Systems

Invite Marginalized Speakers To Talk About Their Research

Use Remote/Hybrid Model as an Advantage

Compensate Speakers

Sustain Your Efforts

Box 2. Summary of strategies we propose to increase the diversity of seminar series.

Benefit to Speaker	Benefit to Members of Host Department
Promoting research program	Exposure to new research, including unpublished work
Feedback from audience	Opportunity to ask questions about the research
<i>Networking</i>	<i>Networking</i>
Attract future grad students, postdocs, and collaborators	Grads/postdocs interact with a potential future employer
Additional presentation on CV	Exposure to new experiences, viewpoint, perspectives, and careers as scientists

Table 1: Benefits of seminars for speaker (left column) and host department (right column). Italicized items are impacted by changing from in-person to remote seminars.

Costs to Speaker	Costs to Members of Host Department
Disruptions to work week-e.g. jet lag	<i>Monetary cost for transportation, housing, food, and honorarium</i>
<i>Travel time</i>	Time and labor to nominate, invite, and organize speaker visit
Preparation time-create or modify presentation, practice time	
<i>Need to arrange for family/child/pet care</i>	

Table 2: Costs of seminars for speaker (left column) and host department (right column). Italicized items are impacted by changing from in-person to remote seminars.

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